

Assessment of Leguminous Tree Capacity in Mitigating Global Warming in Nigeria's Savannah Agroecological Zone in Biu, Borno State Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the potential of leguminous trees in mitigating the impacts of increasing global warming, especially within Nigeria's savannah agroecological zone. With the aid of a soil auger, composite samples were systematically obtained twelve (12) points away from trees, having interval distances of 5, 10, and 15 metres, at three different soil depths: 0-15cm, 15-30cm, and 30-45cm. The samples were taken for laboratory analysis. Results indicate that the soil organic matter (SOM) was progressively higher within the leguminous tree biomass coverage and decreased from the trunk to the canopy margin, except for soil pH and moisture. To mitigate the effects of global warming, the study recommends integrating at least 25 different leguminous trees per hectare into the farming systems in Nigeria's savannah agroecological zone.

Keywords: *Agroecological, biomass, carbon, leguminous, organic, savannah.*

Introduction

The role of agroforestry cannot be overemphasized in soil fertility maintenance in both forest and savannah agroecological zones. The efficiency of spatially integrated trees on crops is influenced by leaf litter quality and quantity, season, rate of decomposition, degree of heat, and soil moisture-related characteristics such as structure, organic matter, and nutrient movement. The potential of perennial tree roots to absorb nutrients beyond the capacity of annual crops and deposit them to soil surface through litter makes their integration into cropping relevant in soil fertility maintenance. Rhoades (1997) opines that synchronizing the release of nutrients from decomposing leaf litter with crop nutrient uptake requirements depends on both the phenology of the leaf drop and litter quality. Tomlinson *et al.* (1995) also observed that in semi-arid areas, farmed trees are rarely planted deliberately; rather, naturally regenerating trees are protected during tillage operations. There are many species of trees in the semi-arid region of Nigeria with various degrees of soil-improving attributes, especially the nitrogen-fixing ones; however, *Faidherbia albida* remains the best soil-improving tree across sub-Saharan Africa. Yields of maize, millet, groundnuts, and sorghum range from 30% to 200% higher beneath *F. albida* canopies compared to the surrounding areas

(Saka *et al.*, 1994). Indications from several studies across the globe highlight the significant impact of leguminous trees, especially in terms of litter production, in adequately meeting most crops' requirements. While crops grown within proximity to leguminous trees may benefit from nutrients released into the soil through litter decomposition, there is a gradual decline in soil nutrient availability with increasing distance.

In many parts of sub-Saharan Africa, where insurgency is prevalent, accessibility to inorganic fertilizers to complement soil fertility deficiencies has reduced significantly, despite the expansion of land-use for crop cultivation. This has led to the degradation of soil fertility, hence, the low productivity of many agricultural produce in Northeast Nigeria. Soil in Northern Nigeria has physically, chemically, and biologically degraded beyond the singular recovery methods and is the basis for the adoption of combined soil fertility management strategies. Abject poverty and insurgency activities ravaging the region limit farming capacity and access to organic fertilizer to complement natural soil fertility. Additionally, overdependence on organic fertilizer has been predominant, with less emphasis on indigenous methods of soil fertility improvement.

One of such indigenous methods is the integration of Sudano-Sahelian-friendly (leguminous) trees into the farming system, an

avenue to restore subsurface-trapped nutrients through eluviation and illuviation processes. Undoubtedly, agroforestry systems improve soil fertility; however, previous studies have not adequately examined the variations in soil nutrient compositions at different distances from leguminous trees. This gap calls for empirical evaluation of soil physicochemical properties within distances from leguminous tree trunks. Consequently, this study investigates how soil nutrient concentrations decline with increasing distance from leguminous trees using Biu Town as a case study.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Biu town is one of the local government areas in Borno State, situated between latitudes 10°34'N and 10°40'N of the Equator and longitudes 12°03'E and 12°07'E of the Greenwich meridian (Waziri, 2009). It covers a total area of 3,315 km², with a growth rate of 3.5% and an estimated population of 294,459, based on the 2006 National Population Commission census. Biu shares boundaries with Damboa to the north, Hawul to the south, Askira Uba to the east, and Kwaya Kusar to the west (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Insert Map of Biu Local Government Area
Source: Adapted from Nigeria Base Map (2024)

Biu Plateau's geographical location provides a climatic advantage compared to neighbouring communities. The rainy season begins in May and ends in October, with rainfall ranging from 35mm in the northern part to about 55mm in the southern part of the study area. The average temperature ranges between 28°C and 45°C. The vegetation is characterized by savannah agroecology, and the soil is predominantly high in clay content, reflecting its hydromorphic composition during the rainy season. Biu soils are classified into two broad groups: alluvial (hydromorphic) soils found near rivers, and primary soils derived from rocks (Bukar, 2015). Due to the hydromorphic nature of the soil, major procedures and analyzed for physicochemical properties at the Gombe State University Biochemistry laboratory. Soil particles were air-dried, mixed, and sieved with a 2.0 mm sieve for soil particle composition (sand, silt, and clay). Soil samples were analyzed for particle size composition using the hydrometer method (Bouyoucos, 1962). Soil pH was determined potentiometrically in 0.01M calcium chloride solution at a ratio of 1:2, according to Peech and Mclean (1982). Organic carbon was determined using the chromic acid digestion method (Walkley & Black, 1934). Organic matter values were obtained by multiplying the organic carbon value by 1.724, according to Roger (2008). Total nitrogen (N) was extracted according to Kjeldahl digestion and distillation method (Bremner & Mulvaney, 1982). Laboratory results were subjected to descriptive analyses, and average values of the variables were presented in tabular form.

cash crops grown in the area include cowpea (beans), soybean, groundnut (*Arachis hypogea*), sorghum (guinea corn), rice (*Oryza sativa*), and maize (*Zea mays*).

In this study, the physicochemical parameters considered were soil particle size distribution (sand, clay, and silt), soil organic matter (SOM), soil organic carbon (SOC), nitrogen, pH, and water-holding capacity. Twelve (12) points with intervals of 5, 10, and 15 metres from leguminous trees were selected, where soil samples were systematically collected from three different depths: 0-15cm, 15-30cm, and 30-45cm with the aid of a soil auger. The soil samples were stored following standard

Results and Discussion

The study area's degree of acidity ranges from 5.08 to 5.32, with an average value of 5.20, indicating a slight concentration of hydrogen ions. High concentration of hydrogen ions can be linked to many factors, such as incessant burning, application of chemical fertilizers, use of potash to neutralize the activity of soil worms, oxidation, and water holding capacity processes. The amount of each element actually available to the plants will vary with soil pH (Robert, 1996). According to McCauley *et al.* (2009), soil pH specifically influences chemical solubility and availability of plant essential nutrients, pesticide performance, and organic matter decomposition. The higher the value of pH, the higher the concentration of calcium and molybdenum, and the lower the concentration of iron, aluminum, and manganese. Most plants prefer a pH (w) range between 6.0 and 7.5, but will grow outside this range, although yield may be affected (Roger, 2008).

Table 1: Soil Physical and Biological Properties

S/N	Properties	(0-5 metres)	(5-10 metres)	(10-15 metres)	
1	pH	5.08	5.32	5.20	
2	N (g/kg)	10.42	8.95	9.69	
3	SOM (g/kg)	75.64	68.41	72.03	
4	SOC (g/kg)	130.18	124.06	117.94	
5	Moisture (%)	2.23	1.79	12.86	
6	WHC (%)	81.57	72.38	76.99	
7	Soil Textural Class	Clay %	55.28	59.35	57.32
		Silt %	16.59	18.31	17.45
		Sand %	28.13	22.34	25.24
			Sandy-clay	Sandy-clay	Sandy-clay

Source: Author's Data Analysis (2024)

Nitrogen exists in the soil in a relatively simple form, mainly in the form of ammonium, nitrate, and organic matter (Cunhu, 2021). Nitrogen values range from 8.95g/kg to 10.42g/kg within the interval of 15 metres with an average of 9.69g/kg. This may be attributed to the illuviated nitrate-nitrogen (NO_3^-). Proximity may be significant in nitrogen status, where the distance within the range of 5 metres recorded the highest value of 10.42g/kg, and vice versa. Nitrogen is a mobile nutrient in the soil, subject to variation in season, horizon, soil particle sizes, topography, management practice, and the nature of crops grown. The amount of nitrogen applied to the soil is easily digested, and the effect is transferred into nitrate nitrogen, which easily migrates with water due to its low soil adsorption capacity. According to Barros and Schroth (2003), more than 95% of the nitrogen in topsoil usually presents in organic forms. Nitrogen is a part of chlorophyll, and nitrogen-deficient plants have light-green or yellow leaves. Nitrogen is one of the most important nutrients for plants since it is a constituent of proteins and nucleic acids (Robert, 1996). Thus, large quantities of nitrogen are taken up by plant roots. However, 50-70% of the nitrogen available to the plant during one season will be available in the following season via plant residues. Another vital condition that determines the variability of nitrogen is the presence of leguminous shade trees such as *Erythrina poeppigiana*, which can fix about $1000\text{kg}\text{ha}^{-1}$ higher, compared to soils under a non-leguminous shade tree (*Cordia alliodora*).

Soil organic matter (SOM) is the summation of plant and animal residues at various stages of decomposition, cells and tissues of soil organisms, and well-decomposed substances (Brady & Weil, 1999). Following Jenkinson (1988), the term soil organic matter includes all organic substances in soil, both living and dead, although the living organisms (the soil biomass) usually contribute less than 5% to the total SOM. According to Schroth *et al.* (2003), the organic materials that lie on the soil surface, including naturally fallen litter, crop residues, mulch materials, and their decomposition products, are normally sampled and analyzed separately from the soil. Soil organic matter (SOM), as shown in Table 1, ranged from 75.64 g/kg at 5 metres to 68.41 g/kg at 15 metres, with a value of 72.03 g/kg recorded at 10 metres. This was directly correlated with distance from the tree: the closer to the tree, the higher the SOM, and vice versa. The influence of nitrogen on SOM dynamics cannot be overlooked in the SOC and SOM dynamics. They all displayed the same pattern of concentration; higher within 5 metres away from the tree up to 10 metres and increased towards 15 metres. According to McCauley *et al.* (2009), soils high in clay and silt are generally higher in SOM content than sandy soils.

Soil organic matter is a derivative of soil organic carbon, and both are inseparable. Organic carbon accounts for approximately 50% of SOM, so a conversion factor of 2 is commonly applied to estimate SOM concentration. The largest amount of carbon

present on the land is not in the living plants, but in soil organic matter (Fred & Harold, 2009). Organic carbon and organic matter indicate the presence of plant and animal residues as well as soil microflora, including fungi and bacteria. In this study, soil organic carbon (SOC) ranged from 130.18 g/kg at 5 metres to 117.94 g/kg at 15 metres from the tree, a pattern that may be linked to the soil's textural class (sandy-clay). Generally, the higher the organic carbon and organic matter levels, the more porous the soil, which makes it better at enhancing plant growth and moisture retention.

Carbon naturally cycles between the atmosphere and soil; however, this cycle is significantly influenced by anthropogenic activities, particularly deforestation in tropical regions. One third of global soil carbon is found in the tropics. Deforestation and land-use changes in the tropics have a significant impact on the global carbon cycle through increased rates of carbon emission (Silver *et al.*, 2000). The organic carbon contents of terrestrial soils vary between less than 1% in many sandy soils to about 3.5% in grassland soils (Schroth *et al.*, 2003). The soil organic carbon pool is 3.3 times the size of the atmospheric pool and 4.5 times the size of the biotic pool (Gbadegesin, 2011). The global soil carbon pool according to Lal (2004) has been estimated to contain more than four times as much carbon as the biotic pool, and about three times as much as the atmospheric pool. Contrary to widespread belief, the organic matter contents of tropical soils are not generally lower than those of temperate soils. In fact, they vary with: vegetation (higher in forest than in savannah soils); climate (higher in mountain forest than lowland forest); soil texture (increasing with higher clay and silt content); mineralogy (higher in volcanic soils due to the stabilizing effect of allophone on SOM); and soil use (Feller *et al.*, 1991).

The results of this study indicate that nitrogen, soil organic matter, and organic carbon decrease progressively with increasing distance from the trunk of leguminous trees, extending beyond the canopy margin. In addition to the nitrogen-fixing and carbon-sequestering capacities of the trees, low evapotranspiration rates, litter fall, and inputs from bird and animal droppings likely contribute to the higher SOM observed in proximity to the trees. Empirically, soil's physical, chemical, and biological properties improved progressively under leguminous trees. It buttressed Bernhard-Reversat's (1982) work that on sandy Luvisol in the semi-arid zone of northern Senegal, SOC, total nitrogen, and the mineral nitrogen flux showed progressive decrease away from the trunk to the canopy margin under *Acacia Senegal*, *Balanites aegyptiac* and baobab (*Andansonia digitata*).

The increase in the content of organic carbon and total nitrogen in the secondary forest can be attributed to the increase in plant diversity and cover, which provides a large amount of biomass that decomposes to form nutrients in the soil (Deekor *et al.*, 2012). An increase in tree biomass resulted in increased carbon sequestration. Dexter (2010) affirmed that the average tropical tree sequesters 22.6kg of carbon per year. Also, the carbon sequestration potential of tropical agroforestry systems produced a median sequestration value of 95 metric tons per hectare per year. Nevertheless, assuming a media of 95,000kg divided by 125 trees per hectare, one would get 76kg per tree (Oderinde & Afolayan, 2021).

Considering an average of 124.06 kg of SOC for a leguminous tree (Table 1) multiplied by at least 50 leguminous trees per hectare would give a total of 6,203kg per annum. Further multiplication by 50,000 hectares of land proposed for a cattle colony by the Federal Government of Nigeria in 19 northern states totals 31,015,000 kg per state and 589, 285,000 kg on an annual basis.

The role of soil water cannot be underestimated in any soil chemistry. In this study, soil moisture content ranged from 1.79%

at a distance of 5 metres to 12.86% at 15 metres from the trees, having an average of 5.62%, indicating hydromorphic soil conditions. This pattern correlates with the high water-holding capacity observed, which averaged 76.99% and may be attributed to the soil's high clay content. The soil textural class was predominantly sandy clay, with mean proportions of 57.32% clay, 17.45% silt, and 25.25% sand. Despite the study area's location in the savannah, cultivation of hydrophytic crops like swamp rice thrives better than other crops, especially in the plains.

Conclusion

In summary, the role of perennial trees cannot be overemphasized in farming systems, irrespective of location, due to their various functions, such as nutrient-balancing between the atmosphere and soil. The short duration of farming activity in relation to nutrient cycling, as well as the absence of perennial biomass, may be seen as one of the reasons for the low concentration of SOM and SOC in Nigeria's savannah. The roles of trees in atmospheric nutrient fixation, throughflow, stemflow, litterfall, soil-plant and animal interaction, and increase in SOM and SOC highlight the importance of agro-based techniques in curbing excess atmospheric carbon. It is a global warming mitigation strategy in the tropical savannah agroecological zone. In addition to aiding natural replenishment of lost nitrogen through litterfall and nitrogen-fixing, evapotranspiration reduction, leguminous trees serve as wind breakers and support ecological and biodiversity conservation, which are beneficial for global warming mitigation. Therefore, the study recommends integration of at least 25 different leguminous trees per hectare to gradually deplete the excess atmospheric carbon, the root cause of global warming.

Acknowledgement

We appreciate the management of the Nigerian Army University, Biu, and the Directorate of Research, Innovation and Development for the consideration and recommendation of this research for institution-based research work for TETFund sponsorship.

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